

Siam 29/Leaung 152 and their derivatives. The Andhra Pradesh population represented biotype 1.

Apparently, the resistance in Phalguna and Surekha has broken down in response to a new, more virulent biotype.

Other resistant varieties involving donors other than Siam 29 also were affected by the new population. In small minikit plots, Pothana (an Eswarakora derivative) and IR36 (a Ptb derivative) exhibited 40.6% and 22.2% silvershoots. These preliminary studies point toward a possible "new" biotype of GM. □

Some common predators of rice insect pests

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We collected predators from ricefields using sweep nets and took visual counts

Some insect predators of rice insect pests recorded at BRRI farm, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1981-84.

Predator	Intensity
COLEOPTERA	
Anthicidae <i>Formicomus</i> sp.	
Carabidae	
<i>Ophionea ishii ishii</i> Habu	High
<i>Ophionea indica</i> Thunberg	
Staphylinidae	
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i> Curtis	High
Cicindellidae	
<i>Cicindela venosa</i> Kollar	Moderate
<i>C. grammophora</i>	Moderate
HEMIPTERA	
Miridae	
<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> sp.	Moderate
<i>Tythus</i> sp.	Moderate
Nabidae	
<i>Stenonabis</i> nr. <i>tagalida</i> Stal	Low
Gerridae	
<i>Limnogonus</i> sp.	Moderate
Mesoveliidae	
<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i> (Horvath)	Moderate
Veliidae	
<i>Microvelia douglasi atrolineata</i> Bergroth	High
Pentatomidae	
<i>Zincroma coerulea</i> Linnaeus	Moderate
Anthocoridae	
<i>Orius tantillus</i> (De Motschulsky)	Moderate
DIPTERA	
Chloropidae	
<i>Anatrichus pygmaeus</i> Lamb	Moderate

of insect predators of rice insect pests 1981-84 (see table). A. T. Barrion of the Entomology Department, International

Rice Research Institute, R. Madge, CIE, London, and M. S. K. Ghauri, CIE, London, identified the specimens. □

A new brown planthopper (BPH) biotype in Parwanipur, Nepal

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We multiplied the local BPH population on susceptible TN1 during the 1984-85 winter season. The biotype was identified by screening on differential rice varieties in the greenhouse. We repeated the screening twice, with three replications each. Damage was scored on individual seedlings using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Mudgo and IR26 with *Bph 1*

resistance gene (resistant [R] to biotypes 1 and 3) were susceptible to the Parwanipur biotype (see table). ASD7, CR94-13, and IR36 with *bph 2* gene for resistance (R to biotypes 1 and 2 but susceptible to biotype 3) were susceptible. The Parwanipur BPH population is not biotype 1, biotype 2, or biotype 3. Rathu Heenathi (*Bph 3* gene) and Babawee (*bph 4* gene) were resistant to the Parwanipur BPH biotype, as were Ptb 33 and Hondarawala with two genes (*bph 2 + Bph 3*) for resistance.

The Parwanipur BPH population appears to be a new biotype. The gene complex of IR56 and IR58 is not fully understood. □

Comparison of differential varietal reactions to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3, and the Parwanipur BPH biotype. Birganj, Nepal, 1984-85 winter.

Gene for resistance and differential variety	Reaction to local biotypes of BPH			Reaction to Parwanipur biotype
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	
<i>Bph 1</i>				
Mudgo	R	S	R	S
IR26	R	S	R	S
<i>bph 2</i>				
ASD7	R	R	S	S
CR94-13	R	R	S	S
<i>Bph 3</i>				
Rathu Heenathi	R	R	R	R
<i>bph 4</i>				
Babawee	R	R	R	R
<i>bph 2 + Bph 3</i>				
Ptb 33	R	R	R	R
Hondarawala	R	R	R	R
No resistance gene				
TN1	S	S	S	S

Seasonal changes in the stem borer (SB) *Maliarpha separata* populations

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We studied seasonal population

fluctuations of *M. separata*, a major pest of rice in Nigeria, Jan-Dec 1982 at Badeggi research farm. Ten hills of susceptible variety FARO 11 were dissected at 10-d intervals from transplanting to harvest to count borers.

Insect population was about four times higher in crops transplanted in the dry season (Nov-May) than in the wet